

Modeling air pollution under uncertainty by using deep generative models

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Abstract.

Modeling and forecasting ambient air pollution is a relevant problem because it is helpful for decision-makers and urban city planners to understand one of the main health problems in the urban area, the degradation of air quality due to motorized road mobility. This article addresses data-driven outdoor pollution modeling given limited data about road traffic density and pollution concentration. In order to deal with such a lack of data, we propose a deep generative model able to synthesize synthetic nitrogen dioxide concentration given road traffic density. Specifically, we train conditional generative adversarial networks. The experimental analysis indicates that the proposed approach generates accurate and diverse pollution data, while requiring reduced computational time.

1. Introduction

The growth of the cities that prioritized the motorized mobility is having an undesired negative effect over safety and quality of life of the dwellers. A major concern is the high generation of air pollutants and their impacts on the citizens' health because pollution reduces life expectancy and diminishes the quality of health [1, 2].

One of the major sources of air pollutants in urban areas is road traffic [1, 2]. Thus, it is mandatory having mobility policies that prioritizes urban health while keeping effective and efficient road transportation. However, it is not easy to understand the different phenomena, e.g., road traffic density or weather, that may have implications for the production or dissipation of pollutants. For this reason, there have been different approaches to evaluate the real impact of mobility policies in the air quality [3]. Thus, modeling, predicting, and forecasting ambient air pollution allow policy-makers and urban city planners to provide solutions to this issue.

This article focuses on generative models to model air pollution in a given point of a city, specifically nitrogen dioxide (NO₂). Generative adversarial networks (GANs) are powerful methods to train generative models [4] to learn to represent an estimate of a data distribution given by the training dataset by using unsupervised learning. Thus, the output is a generative model that produces new information units that approximate the original training set.

2. Conditional GANs for pollution modeling

GANs consist of two artificial neural networks, a generator and a discriminator, that apply adversarial learning. The generator is trained to deceive the discriminator by generating “fake” or “artificial” data samples transforming its inputs from a random latent space. The discriminator learns how to distinguish between the “real” and “artificial” data samples. GAN training is formulated as a minimax optimization problem by the definitions of generator and discriminator loss [4]. Conditional GANs (CGANs) are an extension of GANs to deal with labeled training datasets (structured in classes, i.e, each sample has a y label). The idea is to train generative models able to create samples of a given class according to y .

The general training of a CGAN is graphically described in Figure 1.

Figure 1. General CGANs training setups.

The proposed approach applies a CGAN to train a generative model to get spatial pollution data. The CGAN learns the probability distributions of the generated pollutant given the road traffic density (given by a class from 1 to 5, from lowest to highest). Thus, the generative model has the road traffic density class as an input and returns the predicted NO₂ concentration, which is a random value drawn from the probability distribution learned by the generator.

As the CGAN training is defined as minimax optimization between the generator and the discriminator, the training process may oscillate without converging to an equilibrium. Thus, our method tracks the accuracy of the generator after each training epoch in terms of distance between the real and the generated distributions, and keeps a copy of the best generator found.

3. Experimental analysis

The proposed method has been applied to model pollution in Montevideo (Uruguay). The training data set is composed by sensed data (hourly averaged traffic density and NO₂ concentration) in January–February, 2020. Validation experiments were performed in National Supercomputing Center (Cluster-UY), Uruguay [5].

Three different neural networks architectures for the generator and the discriminator in the proposed CGAN: **CGAN-1**, three-layer perceptron (256 neurons per hidden-layer); **CGAN-2**, four-layer perceptron (128 neurons per hidden-layer); and **CGAN-3**, four-layer perceptron (256 neurons per hidden-layer). The generators’ input layer has size 65 (64 for reading the random latent space and one for the traffic density label) and output layer has size one (for the predicted NO₂ concentration). The input layer of the discriminator has size two (for the label and the NO₂ concentration) and the output layer has size one. The main goal of the experimental evaluation is analyzing the impact on the quality of the results and the computational cost. Table 1 reports the distance between the synthesized data and the real data distributions (*min distance*), the computation time of an independent run (*computational time*), and the training epoch the generator created the most accurate pollution distribution (*iteration best found*).

CGAN type	<i>min distance</i>			<i>computational time</i>			<i>iteration best found</i>		
	min	mean	std	min	mean	std	min	mean	std
CGAN-1	0.41	0.43	0.01	318.41	677.11	179.07	21.00	234.61	140.40
CGAN-2	0.42	0.43	0.01	318.99	827.67	173.34	51.00	165.13	85.04
CGAN-3	0.41	0.43	0.01	341.83	859.05	106.43	20.00	146.10	96.90

Table 1. Experimental results in terms of best generator found and computational cost.

Results on Table 1 indicate that three proposed CGANs generate accurate distributions with the same quality (non-significant differences between them). Focusing on the computational cost, on the one hand, CGAN-1, the smallest model, shows the shortest run times. On the other hand, CGAN-3 finds the best generators faster than the others.

Figure 3 shows real data and sample distributions obtained. The computed distributions indicate that our method is able to capture the general behavior of the NO₂ concentration given the traffic class (the concentration increases with the road traffic). The real data is more dispersed than the synthesizes one.

Figure 2. Pollution data distribution given road traffic class.

References

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